

PROBLEMS OF MODELING AND COGNITION OF THE „WORLD VIEW” AND COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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A man strives to create simple and obvious world view by using adequate methods. This strive implies an attempt to create „view „and to find convenience and self-confidence in it.

It is impossible to act sensibly without the rationalization of the world. The Structure of the universe creates the prism through which people see the world and themselves. By naming objects and events existing in the real world, determining their place in the world, a man „fits” the real world. This is the way the view of some ethnic group’s representatives on their existence is created.

Men’s experience and knowledge is recorded in the linguistic system. In the process of mastering the above mentioned system, people absorb the experience generalized in language. He does not invent the definition of the words- a man applies already existing values set in time and space, a man applies the classification system given in native language. Just for this reason, language affects the process of gaining knowledge and performing activity.

Keywords: *linguistic system, knowledge, language.*

The most valid statements among the numerous concepts on the essence of the lingual world view are the following:

1. Lingual division of the world is different in different nations;
2. Subjective image of the exiting world is formed in human consciousness during human activities;
3. A man adopts the language as well as the surrounding world;
4. Next to the logical image of the world arises linguistic one which doesn't contradict to logic, but still it not identical to it.

The lingual world view is determined as lingual image of the actual subjects and relations, peripheral areas of verbal performance, being the additional source data on our surrounding reality.

The world view is determined by reflecting the peculiarities of solving the problem of existence with the help of the language; Two approaches are identified.

According to the representatives of the first approach, there is no difference between the semantic systems of different languages as far as the reflection of the reality is based on the universal logical principles and

categories. It is possible to identify the regulations:

1. Language reflects the world objectively;
2. All nations exist in the united field of existence and create the whole mankind;
3. Existing difference between different cultures and languages of the nation have accidental character;
4. Despite the existing difference between languages and cultures, adequate perception of information is still possible;
5. Logical categories represent the core of expressing lingual world view.

The second approach focuses on the Sapir-Whorf's hypothesis of linguistic relativity and Vaisgerber's views:

1. Language reflects the world in a subjective way;
2. Nations exist in various fields of existence and don't create the whole mankind. The existing difference between different cultures and languages and nation has non random character;
3. Due to the existing difference between languages and culture it is impossible to adequately convey the information.

Physical, philosophical and linguistic interpretation of the world view creates the basis for the analysis of the lingual world view. Language directly participates in two interconnected processes in terms of the world view:

1. Firstly - the lingual world view is formed within the language;
2. Secondly - Languages itself expresses other images of the human world. The mentioned images enter with specific

vocabulary. They bring the characteristics of the man and his culture in the language. The knowledge based on the individual experience with the help of the language is transformed into linguistic collective achievement and experience.

Linguistics forms the relation with the world view and language, studies the content fixation methods, in other words, the lingual world view, formulated on the basis of the conceptual world view. The world view as the subjective image of the objective reality is revealed in the form of signs.

The primary purpose of the cognitive linguistics is to link the linguistic form to mental representation. The structures fixed in the language represent the structures of human experience, world perception and assessment, recognized by each member of the specific lingual society.

The problem of the cognitive linguistics can be defined through the analysis of the following issues:

1. The essence of cognition: cognition represents the force that supports the process of view formation. Cognition regulates the usage of definitions within the specific culture. Under the definition regulations we mean giving awareness to definitions for every member of society. The awareness of definition is connected to social and cultural experience of a man;
2. The essence of information processing system: cognitivism discusses a man as a processing system of information. Functioning of this system means to acquire, process, save and mobilize the

information. These actions are aimed at adequate solution of the reasonable task;

3. Differentiation of „definition” and „information”: definition and information are radically different from each other: even an non-informative message has a meaning for the information processing system, only informative messages are valid. The message is informative only in the way if it is placed in the advance-compiled code;
4. Peculiarities of language structure: the structure of knowledge is not a static construct – it is constantly formed. The knowledge structure is capable to form the „world view” where we live;
5. The specifics of the cognitive world view: the cognitive world view is realized as the mental model of reality. The mentioned model enables to explain the cause of actions, event prognosis and the organization of human sensitive and rational experience. This is the very form

of experience that is accumulated in the memory;

The relation between mentality and the cognitive world view: mentality is realized as a style of perception and realization of the reality. The peculiarity of the style is stipulated by the peculiarities of the cognitive stereotypes of consciousness. The mentality of a particular person is determined by national or group mentality, as well as by the characteristics of human development, i.e. by his education, culture, event perception and interpretation specifics.

While the main part of cognition is a language, the problem of the cognitive linguistics can be regarded as the space of ratio analysis between cognition and the lingual issues.

The above mentioned analysis implies the research on the contradictions within the continually developing natural cognition on the basis of the world perception and human daily experience.

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Диаграмма соотношения частей:

